

1 **Strategy: While current HPV vaccination approaches present prophylactic promise, a novel,**
2 **integration-site based tailored approach offers therapeutic potential.**

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7 We recently identified expression of sequences from the E5 gene of human papillomavirus type 18 in brain
8 metastatic tissues of humans with non-small cell lung cancer. Currently available papillomaviruses target
9 type 18, but utilize the L1 capsid protein to induce prophylactic immunity. Therapeutic immunity in cancers
10 resulting from papillomavirus infection is not widely studied but a small number of groups have assessed
11 CIN regression in response to experimental HPV vaccine preparations; L1 expression in the tumor clinical
12 presentation is poorly understood but has been observed in a limited number of cases. The proportion of
13 tumor genes that contain integrated papillomavirus genome as compared to those with episomally
14 maintained viral DNA is not completely understood, but traditional estimates describe integration as a
15 prerequisite for transformation. The location of genome maintenance is relevant because the integration
16 event results in clonally-based loss of genome sequences. We propose here the use of non-transforming
17 sequences derived from the E5 gene together with sequences from L1 and or L2 to induce therapeutic
18 response in individuals whose tumors are based on pathologic examination positive for E5 and/or L1
19 expression.
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1 **Discussion**

2 Concept #1: Vaccines can be prophylactic or therapeutic.

3 Therapeutic vaccines utilized widely in the clinic do not currently exist.

4 The mechanism of action of the shingles vaccine can arguably be considered therapeutic but is
5 considered prophylactic. This vaccine utilizes chicken pox virus immunity to prevent re-activation of a
6 latent vaccine. This falls somewhere between preventing a new infection and treating an existing one.

7 Concept #2: Vaccines to prevent infection by high-risk papillomaviruses do exist; they utilize the major
8 capsid protein, L1, which forms a virus-like particle, or an empty pseudovirus. This mimics an infection
9 with the viral DNA. The authentic HPV virion consists mainly of L1 protein, but also contains small
10 amounts of L2 protein. Vaccines currently only contain L1 protein, the major component of the capsid
11 (viral coat).

12 Concept #3: High-risk papillomaviruses cause infections that result in cancer. In other words, high-risk
13 HPV infections can cause cancer.

14 HPV viruses come in many variants, or strains (types), so targeting the correct strain can prevent cancer.
15 Current HPV vaccines successfully prevent cervical cancer in patients that are treated before they are
16 infected.

17 Latent infections can last a lifetime and result in cancer when reactivated (reactivated when maintained
18 episomally, outside of the nucleus, or integrated into the DNA of the nucleus. Currently, it is thought most
19 cervical cancers and other cancers caused by high-risk HPV infections are started when the viral DNA is
20 integrated into the nuclear DNA, whether from a de novo infection or from re-activation of a latent virus
21 coupled with integration of the DNA).

22 Concept #4: It is unknown exactly how many types of cancer in humans are caused by high-risk HPV
23 infections, rather than germline or de novo mutations of tumor suppressors, or germline or de novo
24 mutations/chromosomal events that activate oncogenes.

25 What is known for certain is that nearly all cervical cancers, many or most cancers of the head and neck
26 are caused by alpha genus HPVs, which are grouped together based on their ability or propensity to infect
27 the oral and anogenital mucosa.

28 It is believed but not proven that skin cancer can be caused by a separate type of HPVs, the beta genus
HPVs, which infect cells of the skin.

Concept #5: We recently detected and described the presence of expressed sequences of the E5 gene in
the brain metastases of humans with non-small cell lung cancer. This indicates, and strongly suggests
(but does not completely prove) that lung cancers in humans are, at least in part, caused by HPV infection.

Concept #6: Vaccine strategies that are therapeutic in HPV infection (treating existing infections, rather
than preventing new infections) have been studied to some extent but never approved for use in the clinic.
An effective therapeutic HPV vaccine, given the correct “conditions”, would manage, treat, or induce
partial/full regression of a tumor resulting from an HPV infection, even if that infection is not an active
infection. This therapeutic effect might be observed before emergence of a frank tumor, like during
progression from CIN2 to CIN3; a limited number of studies have shown effectiveness of experimental
therapeutic vaccine preparations in inducing CIN2/3 regression in humans.

1 Concept #7: We stated that “(a)n effective therapeutic HPV vaccine, given the correct ‘conditions’, would
2 manage, treat, or induce partial/full regression of a tumor resulting from an HPV infection, even if that
3 infection is not an active infection.”.

4 What are those conditions? A gene contained with the HPV viral DNA that caused the infection that
5 resulted in transformation would need to be expressed to some extent. This would theoretically present a
6 way to direct a specific immune response to a tumor, because that vaccine would target only the tumor, or
7 only cells infected by an HPV virus, for which clearance would be desired regardless.

8 Concept #8: A novel vaccine preparation composed of viral DNA or expressed, purified protein/peptide
9 containing non-transforming, immunogenic sequences of the E5 gene, delivered itself or with other
10 components of the viral genome that are not transforming - given demonstration of wider expression of E5
11 in primary and metastatic tissues of humans with NSCLC or other types of human cancer caused by
12 high-risk HPV infection - presents a potential strategy or molecular basis for design and delivery of a
13 therapeutic vaccine, complementing existing medical oncology approaches with a novel immunotherapy
14 approach.

15 Note: Viral integration patterns by high-risk HPV viruses are the predominant controlling factor in
16 determining which viral sequences are expressed. A few studies have shown weak expression of L1
17 protein, but it is not currently believed that existing prophylactic vaccines possess therapeutic potentials
18 despite this suggested weak L1 expression by tumors caused by high-risk HPV infection. We found
19 expression of E5 in some metastatic tissues. The exact type and composition of the (whether composed
20 viral RNA/DNA constructs that correspond to expressed protein sequences from specified regions of the
21 HPV genome, like mRNA “transfection” of the S [spike] protein of the COVID-19 human coronavirus
22 mRNA vaccine preparations, or expressed protein/peptide corresponding to these viral genomic
23 sequences) will be determined by these constraints.
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